

APPLICATION OF HIGH IMPREGNATION CHARACTERIZATION OF A CYCLIC BUTYLENE TEREPHTHALATE OLIGOMER RESIN FOR ELECTRICALLY AND THERMALLY CONDUCTIVE COMPOSITES SIMULTANEOUSLY REINFORCED WITH CONTINUOUS FIBER AND NANOCARBON FILLERS

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Keywords: CFRP, Nanocarbon, Cyclic butylene terephthalate, Conductivity

ABSTRACT

Interests in polymerizable, low-viscosity oligomer resins are increasing in fibers and composites fields because high impregnation characteristics of polymer matrices are important for continuous fiber reinforced composites. In this presentation, applications of high impregnation characterization of the polymerizable, low-viscosity cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT) oligomer resin to continuous carbon fiber fabric and carbon nanotube mat composites, respectively, are introduced. High-speed mass production of the continuous carbon fiber reinforced composites (CCFRCs) is required to achieve high-level weight savings by substituting metallic or ceramic automotive parts with CCFRCs. The high-speed production of thermoplastic CCFRCs with a processing time of only 2 min using the polymerizable, low-viscosity thermoplastic CBT resin is proposed. Since a high carbon fiber content of 70 vol % could be achieved with few pores and defects into the CCFRCs caused by the initial low molten viscosity and high impregnation characteristic of the CBT resin, excellent mechanical properties were obtained in the CCFRCs such as a tensile strength of 440 MPa and an impact strength of 44 KJ/m² despite the reduced processing time. Also, the electrically and thermally conductive CCFRCs simultaneously reinforced with nanocarbon fillers were successfully fabricated by modifying the proposed processing. To improve the processability of a thermoplastic carbon nanotube (CNT) mat composite (CNTMC) using the polymerizable, low-viscosity CBT resin, a fabrication method was suggested and the structure-property relationship of the prepared CNTMC were evaluated. Excellent electrical, thermal and mechanical properties were obtained in the in-plane direction of the CNTMC due to the continuously and completely connected CNTs incorporated into the CNT mat filler and composite. The thermal diffusivity in the in-plane direction was $15.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ for the CNTMC prepared under a compression of 36 MPa at 250 °C for 2 min and the result was larger than that of alumina, a ceramic material. The properties were influenced by the internal structure of CNTMC such as the development of the morphology, alignment and weight fraction of the CNT mat within CNTMC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interests in polymerizable, low-viscosity oligomer resins are increasing in fibers and composites fields because high impregnation characteristics of polymer matrices are important for continuous fiber reinforced composites. In this study, the high-speed production of thermoplastic CCFRC was suggested to compensate for the disadvantages of the typical processing of thermosetting and thermoplastic CCFRCs. We selected in-situ polymerizable, low-viscosity oligomer CBT resin to prepare thermoplastic CCFRCs with improved structures and properties under high-speed processing conditions. Also, this study deals with a fabrication method to improve the processability of

thermoplastic CNT mat composites using the polymerizable low-viscosity CBT oligomer resin. In addition, structure and properties of the CNTMCs fabricated by compression molding which may be applied to the fast production of thermoplastic composites were investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The CCFs (CF-3327EPC, HANKUK CARBON, Gyeongnam, Korea) used as reinforcement were made of T-300 grade CFs with a density of 1.82 gcm^{-3} . A CNT mat (Nanocomp Technologies Inc., Merrimack, NH, USA) was also used as the reinforcement in order to produce a thermoplastic CNT mat composite. Individual multi-walled CNTs (MWCNTs) with approximate lengths of 1 mm were grown using a typical chemical vapor deposition method. The MWCNTs were loosely collected using a rolling conveyor system and pressed into a dense mat-like structure. The density of the CNT mat was 0.25 g/cm^3 , and its thickness and free volume fraction were $65 \mu\text{m}$ and 86 %, respectively. The large free volume fraction improved the impregnation of the CNT mat with the matrix. The CBT resin was a mixture of CBT oligomer and a polymerization catalyst. The CBT oligomer mixture made of butylene terephthalate groups which varied in number from 2-7 and resulted in a melting range of 130 - 150 °C with a low molten viscosity of 0.02 Pa·s. Entropically driven ring-opening polymerization occurred in the resin at temperatures above 160 °C, and the oligomers were converted into polymerized CBT (pCBT) [1-8].

2.2 Fabrication

The CBT resin was dried for 12 h at 110 °C in order to remove the moisture which can interfere with the polymerization of the CBT resin. The reinforcements were laminated after sprinkling the CBT powders onto the steel mold. Then, the CBT powders were sprinkled onto the laminated reinforcements and the process was repeated in order to fabricate specimens with the target thickness. The specimens were produced using a hot press (D3P-20J, DAE HEUNG SCIENCE, Incheon, Korea) at 250 °C and a compressive pressure of 1 MPa was applied for 2 min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of the CCFRCs are shown in Table 1, which shows that the tensile and impact strengths of the CCFRCs were enhanced simultaneously by 550 and 400%, respectively, as compared with those of the polymerized CBT (pCBT) matrix. The simultaneous enhancement of the strengths was attributed to the reinforcing effects of the CCFs and the stress transfer between the fillers and matrix. CCFRCs with a high CF content could be prepared owing to the low viscosity and high impregnation characteristics of the CBT resin under high-speed processing conditions. Therefore, the applied high-speed production of thermoplastic CCFRCs has the potential for applications in the mass production of automotive parts.

The thermal diffusivities of the CNT mat and CNTMCs are shown in Table 2. A noticeable anisotropy was observed between the thermal diffusivities in the in-plane and out-of-plane directions. The thermal diffusivity of the raw CNT mat in the in-plane direction was 10,000 times compared with that of the out-of-plane direction. For the CNTMCs, the thermal diffusivity in the in-plane direction was between 10 and 100 times compared with that of the out-of-plane direction. The thermal diffusivity in the out-of-plane direction was insignificantly affected by the processing pressures. However, in-plane direction was enhanced with increasing compression pressure. The result indicated that the excellent thermal diffusivity of the CNTMCs in the in-plane direction under high compression pressure could be achieved to the enhanced phonon transfer along the highly straighten and continuously connected CNT due to the high compression pressure. Heat transfer in CNT composites is known to achieve by phonon transfer and the heat was transported along CNTs in CNT composites and was exchanged at the nanotube tips. The thermal diffusivity of the raw CNT mat in the in-plane direction was between that of copper ($1.14 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$) and silver ($1.73 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$). The thermal diffusivity in the in-plane direction of the CNT mat composites fabricated under a compression of 36 MPa at 250 °C for 2 min was higher than that of alumina ($1.21 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$). The interesting result was

attributed to the continuously and fully connected CNTs in the incorporated CNT mat.

The mechanical properties of the CNTMCs with the processing pressure was shown in Table 3. The tensile strength and modulus gradually increased with increased processing pressure until saturation at compression pressures above 27 MPa. Longer processing and cooling times adversely affected the thermal and mechanical properties of CNTMCs. This result may be attributed to the waviness of the CNT mat filled into the composites in the thickness direction by the applied heat. The optimum processing condition for excellent properties in the CNTMCs was the combination of short processing time, high compression pressure and quenching to induce an ideal structure of the CNT mat in the in-plane direction of the composites.

4 CONCLUSION

Interests in polymerizable, low-viscosity oligomer resins are increasing in fibers and composites fields because high impregnation characteristics of polymer matrices are important for continuous fiber reinforced composites. In this study, the high-speed production of thermoplastic CCFRC was suggested to compensate for the disadvantages of the typical processing of thermosetting and thermoplastic CCFRCs. We selected in-situ polymerizable, low-viscosity oligomer CBT resin to prepare thermoplastic CCFRCs with improved structures and properties under high-speed processing conditions. Also, this study deals with a fabrication method to improve the processability of thermoplastic CNT mat composites using the polymerizable low-viscosity CBT oligomer resin. In addition, structure and properties of the CNTMCs fabricated by compression molding which may be applied to the fast production of thermoplastic composites were investigated. The CBT resin was dried for 12 h at 110 °C in order to remove the moisture which can interfere with the polymerization of the CBT resin. The reinforcements were laminated after sprinkling the CBT powders onto the steel mold. Then, the CBT powders were sprinkled onto the laminated reinforcements and the process was repeated in order to fabricate specimens with the target thickness. The specimens were produced using a hot press at 250 °C and a compressive pressure of 1 MPa was applied for 2 min. The tensile and impact strengths of the CCFRCs were enhanced simultaneously by 550 and 400%, respectively, as compared with those of the polymerized CBT (pCBT) matrix. The simultaneous enhancement of the strengths was attributed to the reinforcing effects of the CCFs and the stress transfer between the fillers and matrix. CCFRCs with a high CF content could be prepared owing to the low viscosity and high impregnation characteristics of the CBT resin under high-speed processing conditions. Therefore, the applied high-speed production of thermoplastic CCFRCs has the potential for applications in the mass production of automotive parts. The optimum processing condition for excellent properties in the CNTMCs was the combination of short processing time, high compression pressure and quenching to induce an ideal structure of the CNT mat in the in-plane direction of the composites.

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	Impact strength (KJ/m ²)
CBT	80	11
CCFRC	440	44

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of the CCFRCs fabricated at 250 °C for 2 min.

Sample	Compression pressure (MPa)	In-plane Thermal conductivity (m ² /s)	Through-plane thermal conductivity (m ² /s)
CNT mat	-	80	0.27
CNTMC0.5	0.5	4.6	0.32
CNTMC9	9	5.9	0.22
CNTMC18	18	8.8	0.23
CNTMC27	27	10.7	0.21
CNTMC36	36	15.3	0.27

Table 2: Thermal diffusivity of CNTMCs.

Sample	Compression pressure (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)
CNTMC0.5	0.5	42	2.8
CNTMC9	9	100	4.7
CNTMC18	18	111	4.6
CNTMC27	27	206	8.5
CNTMC36	36	199	8.7

Table 3: Mechanical properties of CNTMCs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported by the Korea Institute of Science and Technology (KIST) Institutional Program and the Technological innovation R&D program of SMBA [S2177379]. The study was also supported by the Nano – Convergence Foundation [Development of high heat dissipative nanocarbon-polymer composites for 25 W/m·K and its commercialization] funded by the Ministry of Science, ICT and Future Planning (MSIP, Korea) & the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Energy (MOTIE, Korea) and the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Energy (MOTIE, Korea).

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